

Nature of Phenoxides of Niobium(V) and Tantalum(V)

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Phenoxides of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) have been proposed to have dimeric structures on the basis of conductance, and infrared spectral studies. Lewis acid character of these phenoxides has been established by isolating compounds of composition $M(OC_6H_5)_6$. Base with nitrogenous bases. Double phenoxides of composition $M'[M(OC_6H_5)_6]_2$ ($M=Nb$ or Ta ; $M'=Li, Na$ or K) have also been prepared by reacting alkali metal phenoxides in 1 : 1 molar ratio which is supported by conductometric titrations in phenol.

As compared to alkoxides, very little work has been carried out on the metal phenoxides. Only scattered references are available in literature about their synthesis inspite of their utility as catalysts in many industries¹. Kapoor and his coworkers² followed by Schonherr and his coworkers³ have reported the preparation of phenoxides of niobium(V) and tantalum(V), but the structural information about these phenoxides is lacking. In the present investigations, therefore, an attempt has been made to elucidate their structure and also to explore their possibility of behaving as Lewis acid and formation of double phenoxides.

Experimental

Phenol (A.R.) was purified by crystallization from carbon tetrachloride (m.p. 43°). Phenoxides of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) viz. $Nb(OPh)_5$ (m.p. 209°); $Nb(OPh)_4Cl$ (240°); $Nb(OPh)_3Cl_2$ (234°); $Nb(OPh)_2Cl_3$ (196°); $Nb(OPh)Cl_4$ (188°); $Ta(OPh)_5$ (224°); $Ta(OPh)_4Cl$ (253°); $Ta(OPh)_3Cl_2$ (218°); $Ta(OPh)_2Cl_3$ (174°) and $Ta(OPh)Cl_4$ (157°) were prepared by the methods reported in literature^{2,3} and their purity was checked by their sharp melting points and elemental analysis.

Double phenoxides of composition $M'[M(OC_6H_5)_6]_2$ where $M'=Li, Na$ or K and $M=Nb$ or Ta , were prepared by refluxing the components in 1 : 1 molar ratio in carbon tetrachloride for 10-15 hours. The components which were individually insoluble in carbon tetrachloride went into solution on refluxing. On cooling crystalline solid separated out which was filtered, washed with carbon tetrachloride and dried under vacuum. Compounds of composition $M(OC_6H_5)_6$. Base and $MCl_4(OC_6H_5)_6$. Base were prepared by mixing the two components in equimolar ratio in dry carbon tetrachloride when an exothermic reaction took place. The resulting compounds were isolated by the addition of petroleum ether and dried under vacuum. But in case of compounds with pyridine N-oxide and with

triphenylarsine oxide, components had to be refluxed till they went into solution and were recovered by addition of petroleum ether and dried under vacuum.

Infrared spectra of the compounds were scanned as Nujol mulls or KBr pellets on Perkin-Elmer 337 (for 400-4000 cm^{-1}) and Perkin-Elmer 621 (for 200-600 cm^{-1}).

Results and Discussion

The compounds isolated in the present studies are reported in Table 1. All these compounds are moisture sensitive but stable in dry air. They are insoluble in most of the organic solvents except slight solubility in nitrobenzene at room temperature. Molar conductance values of millimolar solution of all these compounds except double phenoxides, suggest that they are non-electrolytes while double phenoxides of composition $M'[M(OPh)_6]_2$ have values which indicate their ionic nature (Table 1). Information on the structure and stereochemistry of the compounds of composition $M(OC_6H_5)_6$; $MCl(OC_6H_5)_4$, $MCl_2(OC_6H_5)_3$ and $MCl_4(OC_6H_5)_6$ has been arrived at by their infrared spectral studies. A significant change has been observed in the spectrum of the pure ligand on complex formation. The lowering of $\nu(O-C)$ present at 1230 cm^{-1} in pure phenol by about 30-40 cm^{-1} is due to the coordination of phenolic oxygen to the metal. The bands at ~ 570 cm^{-1} in case of niobium compounds and at ~ 550 cm^{-1} in case of tantalum compounds (not present in the pure phenol) may be assigned to infrared active (M-O) stretching modes. Such types of bands have been reported earlier in the same region in the case of metal alkoxides^{4,5}. It is interesting to note that in these compounds no band around 900-930 cm^{-1} which could be assigned to Nb=O or Ta=O stretching modes⁶ has been observed suggesting that no oxygen abstraction occurs in these compounds.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE PHENOXIDES OF NIOBIUM(V) AND TANTALUM(V)

Compound	Colour	m.p. (°C)	Elemental Analysis						Molar conductance (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)
			% Found			% Req'd.			
			M	Cl	N	M	Cl	N	
NbNb(OC ₆ H ₅) ₆	Light yellow	<220	12.92	—	—	13.7	—	—	7.83
NaTa(OC ₆ H ₅) ₆	Cream	212	24.15	—	—	23.75	—	—	6.08
KNb(OC ₆ H ₅) ₆	Light orange	115(d)	12.96	—	—	13.47	—	—	6.13
KTa(OC ₆ H ₅) ₆	Light pink	112(d)	24.37	—	—	23.26	—	—	5.62
LiTa(OC ₆ H ₅) ₆	Light pink	212	23.78	—	—	24.26	—	—	5.21
Nb(OC ₆ H ₅) ₅ .py	Light yellow	159-62	14.01	—	2.14	14.59	—	2.19	1.13
Ta(OC ₆ H ₅) ₅ .py	Light yellow	172-75	24.27	—	1.73	24.96	—	1.93	0.85
Nb(OC ₆ H ₅) ₅ .pyNO	Light yellow	>220	13.97	—	2.01	14.24	—	2.14	1.49
Nb(OC ₆ H ₅) ₅ .Ph ₃ AsO	Light brown	>220	9.32	—	4.10 ^b	10.57	—	4.54 ^b	0.97
	yellow		(65.01) ^a			(65.45) ^a			
NbCl ₄ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ .py	Yellow	148-50	21.90	34.43	3.23	22.85	34.89	3.44	1.54
TaCl ₄ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ .py	Light yellow	165-67	36.14	27.98	2.52	36.56	28.68	2.82	0.93
NbCl ₄ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ .α-pic	Light lemon	135(d)	21.87	32.90	3.13	22.09	33.73	3.32	1.46
	yellow								
TaCl ₄ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ .α-pic	Golden yellow	151(d)	34.91	28.01	2.50	35.56	27.89	2.75	0.87

a = % of Carbon ; b = % of Hydrogen.

In case of compound NbCl₄(OC₆H₅)₂, an intense absorption band at 550 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to ν(Nb-O) stretching mode. Since this absorption band is well below the range 570-580 cm⁻¹ observed for terminal ν(Nb-O) stretching mode^{4,5}, this mode

may be assigned to bridging Nb Nb which is in agreement with the previous observations that if polymerization takes place through halogen or oxygen, then the corresponding stretching modes are observed at comparatively lower regions as compared to terminal ones^{6,7}.

A sharp intense band at 350 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν(Nb-Cl) is observed in the compound of composition NbCl₄(OC₆H₅)₂ which is in agreement with the assignments of Djordjevic⁸ and with the reported ν(Nb-Cl) vibrations for octahedral complexes⁹. Thus an octahedral disposition of chlorine and the ligand may be visualized around the metal atom for these complexes. No band which could be assigned to bridged chlorine is observed. In view of i.r. spectral studies particularly in the lower region, a dimeric structure bridging through phenoxy groups can be suggested. Similar observations have been made in case of tantalum complexes as well.

In case of complexes of composition MCl₃(OC₆H₅)₂, MCl₂(OC₆H₅)₃ and MCl(OC₆H₅)₄ molar conductance values of millimolar solutions in DMF (10.25-15.87 ohm⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹) suggest them to be non-ionic. Infrared spectral studies show all the important bands (Table 2) which indicate phenoxy bridging to the metal ion thereby acquiring hexa-coordination. Similar structures have been confirmed earlier also for niobium and tantalum methoxides by various workers^{10,11}.

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF THE PHENOXIDES OF NIOBIUM(V) AND TANTALUM(V)

Compound	ν(O-C)	ν(M-O) or (Δ-O+C-C)	ν(M-X)
Nb(OPh) ₅	1196	552, 576	—
NbCl(OPh) ₄	1198	553, 569	349
NbCl ₂ (OPh) ₃	1204	540, 572	354
NbCl ₃ (OPh) ₂	1198	542, 575	352
NbCl ₄ (OPh)	1201	550	350
Ta(OPh) ₅	1190	520, 548	—
TaCl(OPh) ₄	1196	525, 550	332
TaCl ₂ (OPh) ₃	1208	521, 552	339
TaCl ₃ (OPh) ₂	1200	528, 548	330
TaCl ₄ (OPh)	1204	530	335

Attempts have also been made to establish the Lewis acid character of these phenoxides by isolating some adducts with bases like pyridine, pyridine N-oxide, α-picoline and with triphenylarsine oxide (Table 1). The pure phenoxide which is dimeric through phenoxy bridging reacts with base whereby ring opening takes place. The ring opening is further ascertained from the changes which ν(Nb-O) stretching modes of the pure phenoxide experience on complexation. The band present in the lower region (540-550 cm⁻¹) attributed to bridging

Nb Nb in the pure compound is shifted to higher wave numbers in adducts with pyridine¹². Further, broadening of the sharp bands in the region 570-580 cm⁻¹ attributed to terminal ν(Nb-O) bond on complexation, can be due to either lowering in symmetry around the central metal or to the coordination of nitrogen of the pyridine ring with the metal because ν(M-N) vibration also occur in the region 600-400 cm⁻¹ and these are always associated with the rings deformation vibrations¹³. The ν(C=N) observed at 1578 cm⁻¹ for free pyridine¹⁴⁻¹⁶ shifts to 1610-1620 cm⁻¹ on coordination. The pyridine ring deformation vibrations

were also shifted to higher wave numbers¹⁴. In case of α -picoline, the bands present at 1597, 1572, 1479, 1433 and 996 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ ¹⁷ are shifted to higher regions due to drift of electrons from nitrogen to the metal. Co-ordination of pyridine N-oxide to phenoxides is indicated by the significant lowering of $\nu(\text{N}-\text{O})$ stretching mode from 1265 cm^{-1} to 1221-1230 cm^{-1} on complexation. The trend of shift of other characteristic bands of pyridine N-oxide arising from $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ stretching out of plane vibration of the ring and (N-O) bending mode are in the same direction as reported earlier¹⁹. Since there is only one band assigned to metal-chlorine stretching modes a possible *trans* structure for these adducts may be proposed¹⁹.

Last of all, some double phenoxides of niobium and tantalum of composition $\text{M}'\text{M}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_6$ where $\text{M}'=\text{Li}, \text{Na}, \text{K}$ and $\text{M}=\text{Nb}$ or Ta have been prepared by refluxing the corresponding transition metal phenoxide with alkali metal phenate in 1 : 1 molar ratio in carbon tetrachloride. The stoichiometric composition has been confirmed by elemental analysis and by carrying out conductometric titrations of these solvo acids against solvo bases in phenol at $50 \pm 0.1^\circ$. From conductance-composition curve, it can be seen that there is a sharp break at 1 : 1 molar ratio which confirms the formation of a double phenoxide as :

Similar results have already been reported by Malhotra and coworkers²⁰ wherein titanium(IV) phenoxides have been titrated against sodium phenate in phenol at 50° .

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References

1. TANIGUCHI KATSUO and ARAKAWA TAKKAKI, Japan, *Kokai*, 1971, **73**, 10046.
2. S. PRAKASH and R. N. KAPOOR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 50.
3. M. SCHONHERR, D. HASS and K. BAUFELD, *Z. Chem.*, 1975, **15**, 66.
4. C. G. BARRACHLOUGH, D. C. BRADLEY, J. LEWIS and I. M. THOMAS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2601.
5. D. C. BRADLEY and A. H. WESTLAKE, Proceedings of the Tihany Symposium, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Budapest, 1965, p. 309.
6. C. G. BARRACHLOUGH, J. LEWIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3552.
7. R. J. H. CLARK, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1965, **21**, 955.
8. C. DJORDJEVIC, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1965, **21**, 301.
9. D. M. ADAMS, J. CHATT, J. M. DAVIDSON and J. GERRATT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2189.
10. R. G. REISS, L. G. PFALZGRAF, *Bull. Soc. Chem.*, 1968, 2401, *Bull. Soc. Chem.*, 1968, 4348.
11. D. C. BRADLEY, "Advances in Inorganic and Radiochemistry", 1972, **15**, 259.
12. R. C. PAUL, HARMRET MADAN and S. L. CHADHA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 447.
13. D. M. ADAMS, "Metal-Ligand and Related Vibration", Arnold, London, 1967.
14. N. S. GILL, R. H. NUTTALL, D. E. SCAIFE and D. W. A. SHARP, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, **18**, 79.
15. R. J. H. CLARK, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 350.
16. J. R. DURING, B. R. MITCHELL, D. W. SINK, J. N. WILLIS and A. S. WILSON, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1967, **23A**, 1121.
17. R. H. WILEY and S. C. STAYMAKER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 2233.
18. R. C. PAUL, P. SHARMA, L. SUBBIAH, H. SINGH and S. L. CHADHA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 169.
19. N. J. HAWKINS and D. R. CARPENTER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1955, **23**, 1700.
20. K. C. MALHOTRA, R. K. MAHAJAN and S. C. CHAUDHRY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14A**, 1017.